

Cadmium accumulation on shallot which planted on cadmium contaminated land

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural land contaminated with heavy metals is a serious problem due to its toxic effects and accumulation through the food chain which decrease land quality and disrupt human health. Cadmium (Cd) is one of the heavy metals that are harmful to human health. This research was conducted to determine cadmium accumulation in onion plants grown on Cd contaminated land. This research was carried out in the shallow field in Igirklanceng Village, Sirampog District, Brebes Regency in 2017. Experiments used a Randomized Block Design (RBD), with 3 replications and eight treatments. The results showed that Cd concentration is accumulated in the tubers < stem < roots. The average concentration of Cd in tubers grown on contaminated soil ranges from 1.46 to 2.00 mg/kg. This means that the concentration of Cd in the tubers is higher than the maximum limit allowed to be consumed according to BPOM (2017) which is equal to 0.05 mg/kg so that efforts need to be made to reduce the Cd concentration in the soil intensively until the Cd content in the soil is lower than the maximum limit.

Keywords: *accumulation, cadmium, shallot*

INTRODUCTION

Cadmium (Cd) is a heavy metal that is carcinogenic and toxic or toxic even in low concentrations (Khan et al., 2015a). Contamination by toxic metals in agricultural land can cause stress on plants three times greater than that of pesticides (Jeliuzko, 2001). Cadmium is spread in the environment through among other things, various human activities such as waste disposal, phosphate fertilizer, industrial activities and human settlements (Wagner, 1993).

Heavy metals in agricultural land can be absorbed by plants and accumulated in the roots, leaves, fruits and seeds (Fang and Zhu, 2014). Cadmium accumulation (Cd) in plants can inhibit nutrient uptake (Pardo et al.,

2013), inhibit photosynthetic distribution (Xue et al., 2013; Xue et al., 2014), inhibit photosynthetic rate, enzyme activity, increasing peroxide compounds and causing genetic changes (Dezar et al., 2005).

Cd accumulation in various types of plants has been widely studied and shows a variety of responses. Greger and Lofstedt (2004) examined the uptake and distribution of Cd in roots, leaves and seeds in various wheat cultivars. The results of Sekara et al. (2005) showed that red beet plants were able to accumulate large amounts of Cd in the leaves, while its accumulation in the roots is 2.8 times smaller than in the leaves. In pumpkin plants (pumpkin), the largest Cd is accumulated in the leaves, at least in the stem and fruit. The Cd accumulation in barley roots is 4 times greater than the panicle, and 7 times greater than that found in the seeds. The results of this study concluded that red beet, pumpkin, chycory, common bean, white cabbage and parsnip plants accumulated the largest Cd in their leaf organs. Wang et al. (2007) studied 2 corn cultivars (Nongda No.108 and Liyu No.6), the uptake and concentration of Cd in the roots and shoots of both corn cultivars were different, but both cultivars accumulated greater Cd in the roots than the shoots. Romkens et al. (2009) examined the uptake and distribution of Cd from 12 rice varieties. Sharma et al. (2010) found that the accumulation of Cd in the root of *Pisum sativum* was greater than the shoot portion. The content of Cd in the part of green mustard root, chicory and kailan is greater than shoots (Susana et al., 2013).

A high Cd concentration can reduce content of Ca, Mg, and K in tomato tissue (Khan et al., 2016) and cucumber (Burzynski, 1988). Bioaccumulation of Cd causes changes in various physiological functions by influencing N metabolism (Chaffei et al., 2004). Being an important part of genetic, structural and metabolic components, N plays an important role in plant growth and metabolism (Hasan et al., 2008).

The absorption of Cd by vegetables from the soil is the main exposure pathway for humans (Franz et al., 2008; Kobayashi et al., 2008), and exposure through vegetable consumption to about 70-80% of total intake in humans (Olsson et al., 2002; Yang et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2016). Cd has an adverse effect on the health of the human body where bones and kidneys are the most important target organs (Aitio and Tritscher, 2004).

Consumption of food crops contaminated with heavy metals causes accumulation of heavy metals in the organs of the body that cause various diseases and disorders of bodily functions such as fractures, cancer, damage to

the heart, liver, kidneys, lungs, and mutagenesis that can cause death (Friberg et al., 1992; Portier 2012).

Cadmium pollution on agricultural land in several regions in Indonesia has exceeded the permissible threshold, so it needs to get serious attention by industry players, farmers, and the government. Cadmium contamination can be prevented through good management of industrial waste, reducing excessive input of inorganic fertilizers and pesticides, minimizing soil treatment, water management, planting heavy metal absorbing grass, and strict supervision from the government. Methods of controlling contaminated land can be carried out according to the level of contamination.

This research was conducted to determine cadmium accumulation in onion plants grown on contaminated soil Cd.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was carried out in the shallot farmer land in Igirkklanceng Village, Sirampog Subdistrict, Brebes Regency, Central Java Province, which had a high grade of Cd in 2017. Experiments used a randomized block design (RBD), with 3 replications, and eight treatments as follows:

T0 : control	T5 : biochar + biological fertilizer
T1 : compost	T6 : compost + biological fertilizer
T2 : biochart	T7 : biochar + compost + biological fertilizer
T3 : biochar + compost (biocompost)	T8 : treatment of farmers
T4 : biological fertilizer	

The shallot seeds of Bima Curut varieties were planted in each plot. The size of the plot adjusts to the farmer plot. Biofertilizers, compost, biochar, and biocompost were applied before planting. Compost, biochar, and biocompost were used as much as 2 t/ha (according to the dose used by farmers) which applied before planting during tillage. Biocompost was a mixture of biochar : compost (1: 4 w/w). All of these treatments were applied during tillage, then the soil is left for 1 week.

Inorganic fertilizers of N, P, and K used were 200 kg N/ha, 90 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 150 kg K₂O/ha. As a source of N, P, and K used were urea, SP-36, and KCl, respectively. P fertilizer is given at once before planting. N and K fertilizers are given twice at the age of 15 and 30 days after planting (DAP), each half dose by sowing on each plot of onion plants. Seedlings were planted with a spacing of 15 cm x 20 cm.

The parameters observed were Cd content in the initial soil after ameliorant application and Cd concentration in plants (onion leaves and tubers).

Analysis of Cd content on soil and plants was done at the Laboratory of Agricultural Environmental Research Institute.

Parameters of Cd heavy metal data in soil and plants were carried out in quantitative descriptive analysis. All parameters are analyzed using the Microsoft Excel and SAS Window Release 9.00 program tools.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The availability of heavy metals in the soil is naturally influenced by several factors including: soil pH, soil organic matter content, CEC, and soil type (Sing and Steinnes, 1994). Addition of organic matter can source from organic fertilizer. The use of phosphorus fertilizer is generally considered as one of the main sources of Cd input for agricultural soils (Smolder and Mertens, 2013).

The availability of Cd heavy metal in the soil can be seen in Figure 1. The available metal content of Cd in treatment of biochar + biological fertilizer is the highest as much as 0.441 mg/kg. While the lowest of Cd availability is treatment of biological fertilizer.

Figure 1. Cd concentration in soil on different treatments

Shallot plant growth can be referred with parameters of plant height and number of leaves. The height of shallots up to 70 days after planting (DAP) is

still increasing as shown in Figure 2. The number of leaves up to 70 days after planting is still visible (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Shallot plant height in several treatments

Note :

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|--|
| T0 : control | T5 : biochar + biological fertilizer |
| T1 : compost | T6 : compost + biological fertilizer |
| T2 : biochart | T7 : biochar + compost + biological fertilizer |
| T3 : biochar + compost (biocompost) | T8 : treatment of farmers |
| T4 : biological fertilizer | |

Figure 3. Number of onion plant leaves

Cd metal has a significant negative impact on the nutritional value of plants and growth rate in most plants grown in contaminated soil Cd. The significant negative impact affects nutrient deficiency in plants (Khan et al., 2015b). As shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3 in the T5 treatment, it grows delayed with most other plants. The greatest possibility of this is caused by the highest presence of available Cd concentration in soil than other treatments.

Heavy metals enter plant cells through the same transportation as the system used to absorb the macro and micronutrient elements needed by plants. So it is necessary to make efforts to maintain the condition of agricultural land so that the heavy metal content in it does not exceed the critical limit that has been determined.

The concentration of Cd metal in the roots, stems and onion bulbs can be seen in Table 1. The average concentration of Cd metal in the roots, stems and onion bulbs is 2.16-2.93 mg/kg; 2.12-2.44 mg/kg; 1.46-2.00 mg/kg, respectively. The highest accumulation of Cd Cd is in the root but the lowest is in the tuber.

Table 1. The content of Cd heavy metals in shallots

Treatment	Total Cd (mg/kg)		
	Root	Stem	Tuber
T0 : Control	2.23a	2.12a	1.71a
T1 : Compost	2.86a	2.19a	1.81a
T2 : Biochar	2.43a	2.44a	1.63a
T3 : Bio compost	2.36a	2.29a	2.00a
T4 : Biological fertilizer	2.93a	2.38a	1.65a
T5 : Biochar + biological fertilizer	2.16a	2.18a	1.70a
T6 : Compost + biological fertilizer	2.40a	2.34a	1.60a
T7 : Biocompost + biological fertilizer	2.55a	2.64a	1.46a
T8 : Treatment of farmers	2.38a	2.57a	1.59a

Note: The values followed by the same letters are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$ by DMRT. Lowercase letters are read vertically (columns) and capital letters read horizontally (rows).

The concentration of Cd metal in roots can cause nutrients deficiency by competing for nutrient absorption which have similar chemical properties such as Ca and Mg (Barcelo and Poschenrieder, 1990). A high Cd concentration can cause reduction Ca, Mg, and K in tomato tissue (Khan et al., 2016) and cucumber (Burzynski, 1988). Bioaccumulation of Cd causes changes in various physiological functions by influencing N metabolism (Chaffei et al., 2004). The

Element N is an important part of genetics because it plays an important role in the growth and metabolism of plants.

The average value of metal Cd accumulation in shallot tubers is 1.46-2.00 mg/kg. This concentration is higher than the maximum limit that is allowed to be consumed according to BPOM (2017) that is equal to 0.05 mg/kg. Cd metal will be gradually accumulated in the human body and eventually cause a variety of adverse health effects especially causing bone damage and nephron toxicity (Nordberg et al., 1991; WHO, 1992).

CONCLUSIONS

1. The shallot absorbs Cd from soil and be accumulated in the tubers < stems < roots.
2. The Cd concentration in tubers is 1.46-2.00 mg/kg which is higher than the maximum allowed for consumption according to BPOM (2017) which is 0.05 mg/kg.
3. There needs to be further research to intensify the concentration of Cd in the soil intensively until the Cd content in the soil is below the prescribed maximum limit

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